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Overarching Questions, New Approaches & Technologies in Mixoplankton Research

Mixoplankton International Conference WORKSHOP REPORT 21 January 2021

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Timetable & Agenda

	Time GMT	TOPIC
	11:30	ARRIVAL & WELCOME
Session 1	Chair: Patricia Glibert	Rapporteur Kevin J Flynn
	12:00	Mixoplankton Overarching Questions
	13:20	BREAK
Session 2	Chair: Tim Smyth	Rapporteur: Aditee Mitra
	13:30	Mixoplankton New Approaches and Technologies
	14:50	Wrap up
	15:00	END

Claudia Trapani

PROTOZOOPLANKTON

Protist plankton that engage in different forms of heterotrophy (e.g., osmotrophy, phagotrophy) in the one cell. Protozooplankton are not mixotrophs.

Claudia Trapani

PHYTOPLANKTON

Ubiquitous protist plankton that engage in photo-autotrophy and osmo-heterotrophy in the one cell. All phytoplankton are mixotrophs but all mixotrophs are not phytoplankton.

Summary Report

A glossary is given at the end of this document

Introduction

The workshop was held *in silico* using Zoom Meetings. There were 45 attendees (listed at the end of this document). The workshop sought to explore a series of topics identified from issues raised by various authors and referees to recently published or submitted papers, and by interactions with stakeholders. What follows is a distillation of discussion on headline topics raised by the session Chairs, contextualised by other views expressed during the MixITiN Conference (which had been held over the previous 2 days), followed by a brief commentary upon other topics discussed.

Session 1: Overarching Questions

The mixoplankton paradigm – is it significant? How do we make that judgement?

This is perhaps the most profound question concerning the paradigm – *does it matter?* No consensus was reached on the question of what constituted ‘significant’, whether a change in productivity of 5, 10, 20% by involvement of mixoplankton would be considered to be of consequence. Workshop participants were reluctant to speculate, underscoring the need for more data and more metrics that can be evaluated. Productivity is one metric; biomass is another. Impacts on fisheries or biodiversity or HAB toxicity are other examples, but no synthesis or consensus yet exists for how to estimate/quantify significance.

What was agreed was that resolution to this question was most likely to come from building simulation models with inclusion of mixoplankton and testing for the consequences of then excluding them for the dynamics of biogeochemistry or fisheries production. This requires an expenditure of effort in not only describing mixoplankton functional groups in an appropriate fashion in those models, but also (and agreed as equally importantly) ensuring that other members of the plankton community (e.g., zooplanktonic grazers) are also adequately (appropriately) described.

How can we use our current and emerging tools to understand/quantify the balance of photo- and phagotrophy in mixoplankton?

While we have not been able to identify clear tools to answer this question, within MixITiN we have identified a range of traditional methodologies which cannot be used to answer this question. The consensus reached at the workshop was that we, therefore, appear little further down the road to being able to answer this question than at the start of MixITiN three years ago. What is apparent, is that for many constitutive mixoplankton the acquisition of C by phagotrophy is likely of secondary or minor consequence, but that feeding for nutrients such as P is of most importance. The question on the ‘balance of photo- and phagotrophy’ is thus posed in inappropriate units (and likely also speaks to mixoplanktonic nutrition not being an additive physiological event, but one of synergy). The question as originally posed appears more applicable to non-constitutive mixoplankton, notably for ciliates for which significant flows of C indeed come both from predation and acquired phototrophy.

Are we measuring the right things?

The answer to this question is largely yes, but that the effort is very heavily skewed against informing the models that all agreed are pivotal in answering the question, ‘*does it matter?*’ It was pointed out that the

vast bulk of developmental efforts are essentially directed at '*who is there?*', less on '*how many?*' (and hence the biomass distribution), and far less on determining '*what they are doing?*' (rate processes). It is the last mentioned that is of especial importance to support modelling.

The primary molecular effort (barcoding) contributes to '*who?*', but even that is problematic (especially for modelling) as the detail can be confusing and overwhelming. There appears to be, even after 30 yrs, still little if any evidence of molecular tools contributing to the estimation of rate processes beyond indicating a potential for physiological activity. The dearth of direct measurement of rates (C-fixation, grazing, nutrient assimilation, respiration) for mixoplankton was noted, and there appears little being done to rectify the challenge. A compounding problem for mixoplankton research is the need to simultaneously perform analysis that have traditionally been performed separately by phytoplankton and protozooplankton researchers, requiring equipment and skills not typically coupled together. Furthermore, there are concerns over whether laboratory cultures (especially those held for many years since isolation) have physiologies that still reflect those of their counterparts in nature, and whether experimental conditions in the laboratory align well with those encountered in nature (prior nutrient status, prey types, etc.).

What are the major challenges to modelling?

It was agreed that models are pivotal in making progress. It was also agreed that to make progress requires more than just the activity of plankton and oceanographic modellers. Progress requires a concerted effort to review descriptions of other plankton members (notably diatoms, whose blooms often precede mature ecosystem development for mixoplankton, and of grazers).

The lack of numeric data usable for modelling is keenly felt. The inability of molecular biology to directly assist in the effort was also noted, though it was acknowledged that molecular biology has played a pivotal role providing conceptual understanding for how mixoplankton have evolved and how individual species function at an overarching level. What remains missing then, are the physiological (rate) studies married to concurrent molecular biology approaches that are necessary to link through to the rate-based mechanistic underpinning of model development.

In addition, there is a need for frequent and relevant field data collection of '*who?*' and critically also '*how many?*', coupled with '*where/when?*' or '*why?*' (i.e., what conditions). These data are required to validate models. For Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), for which specific species and perhaps even strain information is available, targeted model construction may be warranted. However, for most plankton much of the '*who?*' data carries excessive detail for modellers, scientists that for pragmatic reasons must group organisms according to ecological functionality. Readily available and up-to-date information linking species (strain) information to trophic status is therefore essential to correctly compare grouped model results to typical field surveys of species occurrence. It was noted that even for HABs models, an understanding of the allied plankton ecology, and of course hydrodynamics, is also important.

Session 2: New Approaches & Technologies

This session was centred on questions of ‘why?’, ‘how?’, ‘what?’, and critically, ‘who for?’

Identifying ‘who for?’ has a fundamental impact on various considerations as it involves pragmatic topics such as cost (affecting also technique deployment frequency), together with the skills required in acquisition and interpretation of data. Needs for routine deployment of techniques for environmental monitoring thus differ greatly from those for many researchers, who use specialist highly expensive applications.

However, it was also recognised that even the most basic of routine monitoring can be of great utility in supporting development/exploitation of the mixoplankton paradigm. Many organisms subject to traditional ‘phytoplankton’ monitoring are actually mixoplankton so gains are possible by simply repurposing extant infrastructure and data analyses with sufficient guidance and effort to better understand the implications of mixoplanktonic nutrition.

Why do we want to measure mixoplanktonic activity and how do we do this?

The underlying answer rests in the hypothesis that mixoplanktonic organisms, due to their synergistic approach in acquiring resources, gain an advantage over other organisms that depend on a single approach (e.g., phototrophy or phagotrophy). Understanding the underlying principles governing such exploitation may be of benefit to ecosystem services – e.g., ‘good mixoplankton’ as food for fish versus ‘bad mixoplankton’ causing toxic harmful blooms (HABs) or ecosystem disruptive blooms (EDABs).

The development of methods to track mixoplankton and their activities is thus linked fundamentally to why we wish to undertake the analysis – e.g., specific HAB monitoring, plankton community monitoring to aid fisheries or climate change monitoring. The ‘how do we do it?’ is then associated with ‘who?’, ‘how many?’ (i.e., biomass and allometry), and then the contributions of phototrophic and/or phagotrophy activity.

Simply knowing ‘who?’ and ‘how many?’, together with an understanding of the potential for mixoplanktonic activity in different species has considerable potential for advancing routine monitoring. Such knowledge and understanding would aid in gaining awareness of processes which could promote or hinder growth and proliferation of different plankton species, processes which may have hitherto been unknown under the traditional phytoplankton-zooplankton paradigm.

Below, we present the different methodologies that were discussed.

Remote sensing

Often seen as a panacea for monitoring, remote sensing even for simply estimating chlorophyll levels provides only an overarching feel for events. It does however provide data for spatial and temporal variability unavailable by any other means albeit only in the uppermost water layer and subject to weather conditions. However, mixoplankton appear to have lower Chl:C than do diatoms, the model organisms for remote sensing, and they often frequent deeper zones in the water column, exploiting material at water layer boundaries. Outwardly, then, remote sensing likely has limited potential in resolving questions over the importance of the mixoplankton paradigm. However, some leverage may be gained by linking remote sensing signals to other essential ocean variables (EOV; e.g., temperature, salinity, O₂, etc.), and thence to changing hydrographic features conducive to the development of mixoplankton-friendly mature ecosystems from immature systems, and decadal changes in colour patterns linked to climate-change.

Platforms: buoys, gliders

While the potential for such autonomous platforms in plankton research is clear, how they would actually contribute to mixoplankton science or monitoring is far from clear. What is needed are robust, ideally solid-

state, instruments measuring parameters other than Chl and the standard suite of EOVs. As discussed below, such challenges are significant even for standalone instruments in a laboratory situation. Like other high volume data producers, likely some level of Artificial Intelligence (AI) would be required to help make an initial scan of data for proxies of mixoplankton presence and activity. Of course to do that requires sufficient data and understanding to enable us to train the AI in the first instance.

Optical and allied approaches

Photosynthesis characterisation equipment such as Fast Repetition Rate fluorometer (FRRf) and PhytoPAM type instruments provide data for photosynthetic efficiencies, cross sections (PSII) and rapid light curves, providing proxies for primary production and PE curves. However, there are no instruments that provide a counter coverage of phagotrophy. Phagotrophy, and grazing in general, still requires extensive experimental manipulations for which we still do not understand the full implications of mixoplanktonic activity either. This challenge is of equal importance for research on protozooplankton, and indeed on mesozooplankton. These rate determinations are of critical importance in connecting phytoplankton and mixoplankton primary productions through to fisheries.

Flow cytometry can provide indications of species size and abundance, and is also useful for grazing rate determinations in bacterivorous mixoplankton; it is especially useful if allied to labelling approaches. There are a number of instruments which are used in ascertaining plankton size and biomass. Coulter counters provide excellent size spectrum and number parameterisation but with no indication of what is actually present; use of this instrumentation needs to be coupled with microscopy and expertise in taxonomy. FlowCAM, a fluid imaging device, provides potential for species identification, enumeration and biomass (especially if aided by adequately trained AI), but its cost and the logistics of operation presents severe obstacles to widespread and routine usage. Similar caveats afflict Cytobouys and similar instruments. There is a particular challenge between the resolution of Fluorescence-Activated Cell-Sorting (FACS) flow cytometry and FlowCam instruments which means that the smaller mixoplankton (<5 μ m) are likely to be neither well identified nor sized adequately. It was noted that the challenges identified here are not just confined to mixoplankton; they apply to all plankton and it was agreed that the whole spectrum of analytical tools directed at the plankton community requires a reassessment in the light of the proposed mixoplankton paradigm.

Molecular techniques

Molecular techniques range from meta-barcoding of whole communities down to single celled applications of 'omics allied to other technologies such as NanoSIMS. The potential appears vast, as is the cost and the demands on skills required to exploit the methods. As noted above, there is also a critical blockage in the pipeline of information flowing from such approaches to rate determinations and thence to models of population activity. Variability between physiological measurements taken in replicate litre volumes are well known, and yet with molecular methods we can examine activities within individual cells where statistical variation between cells must also be large but, for pragmatic reasons, is poorly (if at all) characterised.

The route forward, as noted above, appears to thus use molecular tools to inform the construction of conceptual and thence mechanistic simulation models. Use of those models will flag which aspects of the physiology are of greatest consequence; models should not be solely viewed as an end point.

Such challenges are not specific to mixoplankton research by any means. However, the extra physiological complexity presented by mixoplankton does arguably lend itself most obviously to single-celled analysis. The route through 'omics to physiology, functionality and thence to ecology for microbial plankton has been long promised but now requires delivery, coupled with cross-comparison with traditional bulk analyses which at least have the potential for real time automation.

Other discussion points

Engagement with stakeholders, drawing the importance of mixoplankton, and of the mixoplankton paradigm, to the attention of managers and politicians, requires clarity in technical language and in the overarching science. It also requires simple, robust, cheap, yet meaningful protocols to be developed for routine deployment. These may at least provide proxies for the activity of mixoplankton, related to repurposed combinations of traditional measurements such as Chl, other EOVs, and perhaps readily identified key species (not necessarily mixoplankton per se, but indicators of mature ecosystems that would support different mixoplankton groups or species).

Conclusion

There is an increasing (and arguably belated) recognition that routine monitoring of zooplankton as well as phototrophic plankton is important in determining the health of coastal waters. Mixoplankton contribute to both primary and secondary productions (in crude terms, as 'phytoplankton' and 'protozooplankton' in one cell). The role of mixoplankton to food webs is important in a positive way as food organisms as well as for their negative impact as harmful and disruptive blooms (HABs and EDABs). Mixoplankton should be viewed as indicators of ecosystem health, not just of harmful conditions. The underlying basis for inclusion of mixoplankton is there; progress appears more limited by the need for a well-argued case in a language appropriate for stakeholders likely built in collaboration with those stakeholders. And, of course in the new deployment &/or re-purposing of traditional methods to monitoring.

List of Attendees * Chairs ** Rapporteurs

NAME	INSTITUTE
Aditee Mitra**	Cardiff University, UK
Kevin J Flynn**	Plymouth Marine Laboratory, UK
Pat Glibert*	Horn Point Laboratory, UMCES, USA
Tim Smyth*	Plymouth Marine Laboratory, UK
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Bob Sanders	Temple University, USA
Dave Caron	University of Southern California, USA
Diane Steocker	Horn Point Laboratory, UMCES, USA
Enric Saiz	ICM-CSIC, Spain
Fabrice Not	SBR Roscoff, France
Fernando Unrein	INTECH Buenos Aires, Argentina
George McManus	University of Connecticut, USA
Hae Jin Jeong	Seoul National University, Republic of Korea
Helga Gomes	Columbia University, USA
Joaquim Goes	Columbia University, USA
Luciana.Santoferrara	University of Connecticut, USA
Martina Doblin	University of Technology Sydney, Australia
Matt Johnson	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, USA
Maria Patsalidou	AP Marine, Cyprus
Marina Montresor	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples Italy
Mengmeng Tong	Zhejiang University, China
Michaela Larsson	University of Technology Sydney, Australia
Mike Best	Environment Agency UK
Nathalie Gypens	Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium
Paolo Lazzarri	National Inst Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Italy
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Reza Ahmadian	Cardiff University UK
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Filomena Romano (ESR5)	HCMR Crete, Greece
Guilherme Duarte Ferreira (ESR3)	ICM-CSIC, Spain
Jon Lapeyra Martin (ESR10)	ULB, Belgium
Joost Mansour (ESR4)	SBR Roscoff, France

Konstantinos Anestis (ESR1)	AWI, Germany
Maira Maselli (ESR7)	UCPH, Denmark
Nikola Medić (ESR2)	UCPH, Denmark

GLOSSARY

Terms in italics are described elsewhere in this glossary

- Algal** a non-specific term referring to organisms that are of simple structure (e.g., single-celled 'microalgae') that grow by *phototrophy*.
- Allometry** relating to body size.
- AI** artificial intelligence.
- Barcoding** a molecular biology approach that assigns a "barcode" to organism types; a *molecular biology* -based alternative to traditional taxonomy, although it reports operational taxonomic units (OTUs) which are not directly comparable to species.
- Biomass** amount of organism material per unit of space (e.g., gC m³).
- C-fixation** photosynthesis as strictly related to CO₂-fixation.
- Chl:C** ratio of chlorophyll (Chl) in organisms to their biomass in terms of C; usually with units of gChl gC⁻¹. Monitoring of Chl by *remote sensing* provides a means to estimate the biomass of *plankton* that display *phototrophy* (i.e. *phytoplankton* and *mixoplankton*).
- Ciliate** a type of protist plankton, some of which are protozooplankton and some are (non-constitutive) mixoplankton, which moves using cilia (hair-like appendages); typically 50µm (=0.05mm) long.
- Constitutive mixoplankton** *mixoplankton* that have a constitutive (innate) ability to photosynthesize (Cf. *non-constitutive mixoplankton*)
- Diatom** a common form of *protist* marine *phytoplankton*, with a cell wall of silicate. They are effectively non-motile and often dominant in *immature ecosystems*, with turbulent water that keeps them suspended in the water column. Diatoms are display *mixotrophy* by combining *phototrophy* and *osmotrophy*.
- EDAB** ecosystem disruptive *algal* bloom; a bloom that while not chemically toxic damages the usual flow of energy and carbon through the food web, usually because the organisms are not palatable (Cf *HAB*)
- EOV** essential ocean variables; refers to the standard suite of parameters measured in oceanography (temperature, salinity, turbidity, chlorophyll)
- HAB** harmful algal bloom; usually harmful in a human context, being toxic to humans or to organisms in a fisheries food chain (Cf *EDAB*)
- Immature ecosystem** an ecosystem in which nutrients predominately in an inorganic form, with simple food chains; in plankton ecosystems, typified by the ecosystem during the temperate spring (Cf *mature ecosystem*).

- Mature ecosystem** an ecosystem in which nutrients are closely cycled between organisms which are involved in complex interconnecting food webs, such that residual concentrations of inorganic nutrients are minimal; in plankton ecosystems, typified by temperate summer (Cf *immature ecosystem*).
- Mechanistic model** a computer model for simulation that is based upon mechanistic understanding of how reality functions. In contrast, non-mechanistic models relate observed (often statistical) relationships between variables with no implicit linkage to reality.
- Mesozooplankton** multi-cellular *zooplankton*, typified by copepods, krill and sea jellies ('jellyfish').
- Mixotrophy** obtaining energy and carbon for growth through a combination of autotrophy (usually *phototrophy*) and heterotrophy. Heterotrophy may be supported by the use of dissolved organics (such as sugar), a process termed *osmotrophy*, and/or by eating (which in microbes is performed by engulfment, *phagotrophy*, or similar).
- Mixoplankton** *protist* plankton that obtaining nutrition by CO₂-fixation and by eating. Mixoplankton also display *osmotrophy*.
- Mixoplankton paradigm** a concept that sees the planktonic food web comprising *mixoplankton* as significant components, in addition to *phytoplankton* and *zooplankton*.
- Model** a simplification of reality, but specifically here referring to a computer model that provides a simulation of real or potentially real events.
- Molecular biology** a field of biological science that emphasises the importance of biochemistry linking information held within DNA through to organism physiology (see '*omics*').
- NanoSIMS** a nano-scale mass spectroscopy methodology that enables chemical changes (e.g., associated with the movement of nutrients) to be tracked within an individual cell.
- Non-constitutive mixoplankton** *mixoplankton* that do not have a constitutive (innate) ability to photosynthesize; to photosynthesise they must use either acquired chloroplasts (stolen from their prey) or whole phototrophic organisms held as symbionts (Cf. *non-constitutive mixoplankton*)
- 'omics** a suffix used for various components of *molecular biology* and in general to flag the exploitation of different facets of that subject. e.g., genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics.
- Osmotrophy** a mode of nutrition that involves the use of dissolved organic substrates, such as sugar or amino acids.
- PE curve** photosynthesis-irradiance curve; the relationship between light and photosynthesis (CO₂ fixation, *phototrophy*)

- Phagotrophy** a form of feeding exhibited by microbes, in which food or prey are ingested by engulfment.
- Phototrophy** a form of autotrophy that involves photosynthesis to acquire energy and carbon for growth using light. Organisms displaying phototrophy contain chlorophyll and other pigments that capture light energy.
- Phytoplankton** members of the plankton that obtain nutrition via *phototrophy*. Phytoplankton may be *protists* or cyanobacteria ('blue-green algae'). Phytoplankton can also engage in *osmotrophy*, but not in *phagotrophy* (Cf. *mixoplankton*).
- Plankton** organisms that lack sufficient motility to swim against water currents. Plankton vary in size from the microscopic (ca. $1\mu\text{m} = 0.001\text{mm}$) to large sea jellies of many metres in length.
- Primary production** production of new biomass attributed to autotrophy, and as performed by *plankton* linked to *phototrophy* performed by *phytoplankton* and *mixoplankton*.
- Protist** eukaryotic microbes (contrasting with prokaryotic microbes, such as bacteria and cyanobacteria)
- Protozooplankton** microbial (*protist*) members of the *zooplankton*. Protozooplankton acquire nutrition via *phagotrophy* and *osmotrophy*.
- Remote sensing** a means to monitor large areas from high altitude using cameras or similar scanners sensitive to specific wavelengths, typically associated with satellite or aircraft deployment.
- Zooplankton** members of the *plankton* that primarily obtain nutrition by eating particles of food or prey.